

Monte Carlo Simulation of the Gamma Ray Spectrometer Performance on Lunar Prospector

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Abstract

We present results of a simulation for the GRS instrument response expected in lunar orbit, using 90 spectral lines and a continuum gamma ray background taken from Apollo 15 and 16 data. The Monte Carlo program uses the exact dimensions and composition of the GRS in order to most accurately predict spectral performance, assuming an operating temperature on orbit of -30°C . We expect to obtain a resolution at 662 keV @ -30°C of about 9.6% FWHM. The data set is expected to be 2.5 to 8 times better in terms of peak intensity than the NaI data from Apollo orbiters. This factor depends on the gamma ray energy and is due to the high-Z BGO detector used in the GRS. Both coincidence and anticoincidence data will be returned, and a linear combination of the two spectra will be determined for best peak to background ratios.

I. INTRODUCTION

Monte Carlo simulations have been performed of the data expected to be returned by the Gamma Ray Spectrometer (GRS) instrument of the Lunar Prospector (LP) satellite [1,2]. These predictions will be used as a comparison for the actual data, in order to determine how well the spectrometer is working, and to compare the average equatorial data from Apollo 15 and 16 [3] to the detailed mapped data returned by the GRS. The actual instrument consists of a 3x3 bismuth germanate (BGO) scintillation detector with a top-hat style anti-coincidence shell (ACS) of BC454 plastic scintillator (Figure 1). We expect to obtain a resolution at 662 keV and -30°C of about 9.6% FWHM.

We present results of a simulation for the GRS instrument response expected in lunar orbit, using 90 spectral lines and a continuum gamma ray background taken from Apollo 15 and 16 data. The simulation was run using a version of EGS4 code [4] previously used for silicon detectors [5,6] and subsequently modified for the GRS. The relative line strengths of the elemental constituents and the background intensity (obtained from Bielefeld *et al* [7]) were determined by Monte Carlo simulation of the Apollo NaI detector to match the measured spectrum [3]. The incident spectral intensity was then input into the GRS-specific version of the Monte Carlo code.

The Monte Carlo program uses the exact dimensions and composition of the GRS in order to most accurately predict

Figure 1. The Gamma Ray Spectrometer uses an extremely sensitive bismuth germanate crystal.

spectral performance, assuming an operating temperature on orbit of -30°C . We expect to obtain a resolution at 662 keV and -30°C of about 9.6% FWHM. The data set is expected to be 2.5 to 8 times better in terms of peak intensity than the NaI data from Apollo orbiters for a given observation time. This factor depends on the gamma ray energy and is due to the increased stopping power of the high-Z BGO detector used in the GRS. Both coincidence and anticoincidence data will be returned, and a linear combination of the two spectra will be determined for best peak to background ratios.

II. DATA SETS RETURNED FROM GRS

The main purpose of the GRS instrument provided on the LP spacecraft is to provide mapping of the elemental composition of the lunar surface, as discussed later, in section V. Spectral lines of elements such as potassium, rare earth elements, and phosphorus (KREEP mapping) as well as the radioactive elements uranium and thorium, plus activated lines of iron, silicon, magnesium, aluminum, oxygen, calcium and titanium will be measured in the standard way. Both the BGO detector and the ACS will trigger A/D conversions and accumulate spectra in 512 channel buffers used as a multi-channel analyzers.

Two sets of data specific to the GRS will be returned at each 32 second interval: a BGO spectrum from 0.3 to 9 MeV in each coincidence (rejected) and anticoincidence (accepted) with the plastic shell. In principle the accepted spectrum is the cleanest, since all full energy BGO photopeaks will deposit no energy in the plastic. However, there is additional information in the rejected spectrum which can be used to good advantage with respect to background reduction.

The rejected data consists of gamma rays that had one or more Compton scattering events in the plastic, in addition to the partial peak energy deposited in the BGO. This scattering process mimics the Compton scattering of the elemental spectral emission lines from the lunar regolith before the gamma rays reach the LP spacecraft, and so are similar to the continuum background spectrum which rides below the elemental line spectrum. As such, a properly scaled version of the rejected spectrum can be subtracted from the accepted spectrum to reduce continuum background from the lunar surface. This second data set was not available in previous measurements for use in such background reductions. Figure 2 shows an example of a single gamma ray energy response (2.741MeV), in which both accepted and rejected spectra are shown. Note that the accepted and total counts are identical in the full energy peak (height of 3500 counts, pushed off scale to show detail in the Compton region).

Fig. 2--Example of accepted and rejected spectra for a single line, showing detail in the Compton region.

III. CORRECTION TO ACCEPTED SPECTRUM

The accepted spectrum shown in Figure 2 can be corrected for Compton background by using a scaled version of the rejected spectrum. As shown in Figure 3, the resulting corrected spectrum has the same full energy peak height, since no counts were subtracted there. The secondary peak at the Compton edge can be eliminated with proper scaling. However, for a large composite spectrum sitting on a high background from the Compton continuum due to higher energy lines, the scaling giving the best average background reduction may not be the same as for a discrete line spectrum. In general it is expected that the scale factor will have to be adjusted, depending on how large the experimental background is, relative to the elemental lines. This determination will be made in a future paper [8] in which experimental calibration measurements taken on the flight GRS will be compared to Monte Carlo simulations.

Fig. 3--GRS accepted response corrected by scaled rejected spectra.

IV. ELEMENTAL DATA

The Monte Carlo simulations are presented as a prediction of the type of data expected to be returned by the spacecraft, on average. Limits on identification of spectral features, as a function of observation time, are predicted. Spatial variations in the spectrum over the lunar surface are expected, but cannot be predicted by this exercise since only Apollo equatorial orbital averaged data is available at this time. Figure 4 is an

Fig. 4-- Full lunar spectrum, 90 elemental lines .

example of the full spectrum, in linear scale, expected for the accepted signal from the GRS without background continuum, using Apollo 15 and 16 measured relative isotopic abundances [3]. Figure 5 in logarithmic scale incorporates a continuum

Fig. 5-- Full lunar spectrum, 90 lines plus background.

background in proper proportion to the elemental lines, as calculated from the elemental spectrum decomposition of Ref. 2. Figure 6. shows a comparison of Apollo (NaI) and LP

(BGO) lunar spectra in logarithmic scale, depicting the increase in stopping power of the GRS instrument on LP.

Figure 6. Comparison of Apollo (NaI) and LP (BGO) lunar spectra.

V. ELEMENTAL COMPOSITION MAPPING

The orbital period of the spacecraft is 118 minutes, which yields a ground track of about 50km per 32 second data set. The data will be binned into approximately 150km x 150km pixels over the lunar surface, in order to determine local variations in composition. As the mission progresses over the course of a year, spectral lines will become identifiable in data over each lunar map pixel. The polar regions will accumulate data quickly since the spacecraft will be in a polar orbit.

This Monte Carlo simulation yields predictions of the improvement factor expected after a year of observation and data analysis. The Monte Carlo predictions can be directly compared to the data, since the geometry and composition of the detectors, as well as the noise characteristics and energy binning of the onboard A/D converter are all identical to the LP hardware.

VI. ESTIMATE OF THE OBSERVATION TIME REQUIRED

An overview of the expected mapping time required (last column) to be able to resolve the elemental spectral lines for the given element (first column) is provided in Table 1. These estimates are based on an anticipated nominal concentration of the element (middle column) expected from existing lunar rock and soil data. The times are calculated from an expected efficiency of spectral separation, based on the detection efficiency calculated by the Monte Carlo simulation of the 90 elemental lines plus background. As explained in reference 1, the elemental resolution is a function of the lunar latitude, and occurs quickly at the poles and more slowly near the equator. Times are estimated for full mapping of the lunar surface.

Table 1. Estimates of the observation time required to identify these elements.

Element	Regolith Concentration Range	Minimum Mapping Time
Uranium	0.2 to 3.6 ppm	1 to 2 months
Thorium	1 to 14 ppm	1 to 2 months
Potassium	400 to 4600 ppm	1 to 2 months
Titanium	0 to 7%	3 months
Iron	3 to 13%	6 months
Aluminum	6 to 13%	6 months
Oxygen	41 to 46%	9 months
Silicon	18 to 23%	1 year
Magnesium	2 to 6%	1.2 years
Calcium	8 to 13%	1.8 years

VII. CONCLUSIONS

Monte Carlo simulations of the GRS data expected from the known lunar gamma ray spectrum as measured by Apollo NaI scintillators demonstrates that the important elements of interest in the lunar regolith, such as potassium, rare earth elements, and phosphorus (KREEP), will be measured accurately in less than the full mission lifetime. The increased stopping power of the BGO detector will enable a more accurate determination of elemental constituents than previous data. The additional information contained in the rejected data spectrum will increase the sensitivity of the elemental line measurements by reducing background. The exact scale factors to be used for optimum background reduction will be determined by comparison of Monte Carlo simulations to actual calibration data on the flight instrument, and will be the subject of a forthcoming paper.

VIII. REFERENCES

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